

Polarographic Determination of Stannous (tin) with Acrylic Acid

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Manuscript received 11 May 1981, revised 26 February 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

Stannous (tin) produces a well defined diffusion controlled, irreversible reduction wave in acrylic acid which has been employed for its determination. The limiting current increased with the increase in the Sn(II) concentration. The possibility of determining mg quantities of Sn(II) in solution by this method has been examined. The variation in acrylic acid concentration has no effect on the shape of the polarogram. However, the value of half wave potential shifted to more negative potential with increase in acrylic acid conc. and the pH of solution. The value of half wave potential and diffusion current constant came out to be -0.476 S.C.E. and 3.02 vs, respectively in $0.1 M$ acrylic acid. A 10 fold ratio of In(III), Cu(II), Sn(IV), Pt(IV), Te(VI), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Al(III) and Fe(III) does not interfere. However, Pb(II) and Tl(I) interfere but their relatively lower amounts could be tolerated. The method is one of the most selective.

POLAROGRAPHIC reduction of stannous (tin) has been studied in a number of supporting electrolytes. The polarographic characteristics of stannous are very favourable for practical analytical purposes. The reduction wave in various supporting electrolytes, such as hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, perchloric acid, sulphuric acid, phosphoric acid, sodium fluoride, sodium tartrate-sodium hydroxide¹, ammonium acetate-acetic acid², sodium formate³, hydrochloric acid-ammonium chloride-ascorbic acid⁴, potassium hydrogen phosphate-citric acid⁵ and lactic acid⁶ has been reported. In most of the supporting electrolytes, a maximum appears and it gives a double wave, one anodic and other cathodic. In the present paper, a polarographic method has been developed for the determination of stannous (tin) using acrylic acid as a ground electrolyte. The method does not require external adjustment of pH, maximum suppressor and addition of any other auxiliary electrolyte. Interference of various ion has been studied in detail. Stannic (tin) does not undergo reduction at all in this medium. The method may be used for the determination of stannous (tin) in pure solution as well as in complex mixture.

Experimental

All polarograms were recorded at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a manual Toshniwal polarograph. pH measurements were made with a Philips pH meter. The dissolved oxygen was removed by passing nitrogen through the cell solution for about 5 min before recording the polarograms. A saturated calomel electrode and a dropping mercury electrode with a capillary constant, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ was 1.96 in distilled water and on open circuit were used. Stannous chloride solution and adjustment of pH were made with hydrochloric acid. The resistance of the cell was less than 200 ohms, so no correction for the IR

drop through the cell was necessary. The reproducibility of the half wave potential was ± 1 mV. The experimental conditions were selected to maintain constant liquid junction potentials as much as possible.

The effect of pH was studied in pH range of 1 to 2. The $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative potential with the increase in pH. The reduction wave remained well defined in this pH range. So all the polarograms were recorded at pH 2 as there was no need of pH adjustment.

A variation of acrylic acid concentration from $0.1 M$ to $0.5 M$ had no effect on the shape of the polarogram. The diffusion current decreased while the value of $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative potential with the increase in acrylic acid concentration indicating the increase in the stability of stannous acrylic acid complex.

Polarograms were recorded for different concentration of stannous ($0.2 mM$ to $1.2 mM$) in $0.1 M$ acrylic acid. A linear plot passing through the origin was obtained when diffusion current (after correcting for the residual current) was plotted against stannous concentration, suggesting that this reduction can be used for the quantitative determination of stannous (tin).

Results and Discussion

The effect of the height of the mercury column on the diffusion current was also studied. The linear plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ showed the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction, which was already suggested by the linear plot of diffusion current vs stannous concentration. When $E_{a.e.}$ was plotted

against $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ a straight line was obtained. The slope of this log plot and the value of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$

were both -46 mV and were not in agreement with theoretical values, indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode reduction at d. m. e. Due to this irreversibility no deduction can be made about the nature of the complex formed. The value of I was calculated from Ilkovic equation and was found to be 3.02. This showed that stannous undergoes two electron change during the reduction process. Hence, the reduction can be shown as $\text{Sn(II)} \rightarrow \text{Sn(O)}$. Taking all the experimental observations into consideration, 0.1 M acrylic acid is found suitable for the estimation of stannous.

Interferences: Polarograms recorded in the presence of 10 fold amounts of W(VI), Sn(IV), Pt(IV), Te(IV), Mn(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Cr(III), U(VI), Fe(III), Pb(II), Sb(III) and Tl(I) revealed that only Pb(II) and Tl(I) interfered but their relatively lower amounts (Pb, 0.020 mg and Tl, 0.025 mg) could be tolerated. The results of the analysis of Sn(II) in presence of various ions are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS (1 mg)

Diverse ion	Sn(II)		Error (%)
	Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	
Fe(III)	0.88	0.88	0
Cu(II)	0.88	0.86	-2.2
Pt(IV)	0.88	0.86	-2.2
Mn(II)	0.88	0.88	—
Ni(II)	0.88	0.89	+1.1
Zn(II)	0.88	0.87	-1.1
Co(II)	0.88	0.88	—
Cr(III)	0.88	0.87	-1.1
U(VI)	0.88	0.90	+2.2
Se(IV)	0.88	0.88	—
Te(VI)	0.88	0.88	—
Sb(III)	0.88	0.90	+2.2
As(III)	0.88	0.88	—
Zr(IV)	0.88	0.88	—
Th(IV)	0.88	0.87	-1.1

Simultaneous determination of Sb(III)—Sn(II): As indicated in a preliminary observation, antimony do not interfere under these conditions. Based upon this fact, a method has been developed for the simultaneous determination of Sb(III)—Sn(II). A series of polarograms of solutions of mixed metal ions in 0.1 M acrylic acid were recorded. The value of diffusion current measured for each metal ion was referred to their respective calibration graph as before. The results observed for some mixture are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Sb(III)—Sn(II)

Amount taken (mg)		Amount found (mg)		% Error	
Sb(III)	Sn(II)	Sb(III)	Sn(II)	Sb(III)	Sn(II)
1.2715	2.07	1.2710	2.07	-0.04	0
1.5719	2.97	1.5719	2.90	0	-2.35
1.2715	2.07	1.2700	2.07	-0.11	0
2.1269	2.97	2.1250	2.90	-0.09	-2.85

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